

CONSUMERS ENVIRONMENTAL CONSCIOUSNESS AND ATTITUDE ON GREEN PRODUCTS AS HEALTHY OPTIONS IN SELECTED COFFEE SHOPS IN METRO MANILA

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ABSTRACT

The consumers of the modern-day have turned out to be much more environment-conscious than previously due to the growing global environmental problems. This brought many businesses and goods to jump on the bandwagon and green activities for consumers to purchase "green" products. The present research, therefore, seeks to inspect the consumers' green awareness regarding the pros and cons of green merchandise as well as their use in the decision-making process. Numerous studies indicate that user preference for eco-friendly goods can be a turning point in the success of a company as well as a factor in customer satisfaction, as the study we run shows. This research study has primarily been set to understand how the customers who are usual consumers of coffee in Metro Manila and who are already using green products prefer and are satisfied with the products they purchase. This work is only about 'green' and 'healthy' markets via people's awareness of their environmental concerns and their preferences in Manila's ethical market. The data collected can be used as a basis for measuring the customer's usefulness or non-usefulness behavior for the organic products. This study will have a big impact on the food-related industries, databases, and other researchers in the domain of acquiring a set of related information with the green marketing practice, convinced lifestyle people willing and able to participate in the study leading to the significant relationship, significant effects, and likewise effective outcomes on the given three variables which are environmental concern, health through food safety, and health factors as well as value of health.

Keywords: *Green Marketing, Environmental Knowledge, Sustainability, Green Trust, Healthy Option, Green Products, Green Price, Green People*

INTRODUCTION

Today's consumers are much more aware of the environment than ever before. Global issues include pollution and other environmental difficulties like global warming (Shirsavar & Fashkhamy, 2013). With problems like pollution, biodiversity loss, global warming, loss of forests, etc., on the rise, there is a real danger that the environment may be destroyed. This has led to consumers being more environmentally conscious. Modern consumers are prepared to pay more for things that are beneficial to the environment, they seek companies who have an awareness of environmental issues and employ sustainable practices. Numerous top worldwide companies are implementing these marketing strategies to suit this demand and make sure that consumers have a favorable opinion of their brands. Products that have a positive influence on the environment are now being produced by brands to satisfy consumer demands. Businesses must alter every part of their supply chain as a result of green marketing if they want to become more environmentally conscientious. Its qualities include using eco-friendly products, using eco-friendly packaging, advertising the product's benefits to the environment, and embracing sustainable business practices. Despite the potential for significant expenditures, the benefits that firms can obtain from this type of marketing make them worthwhile. When businesses lead by example, more consumers become aware of the environmental effects of their purchases and have the chance to alter their purchasing habits. As stated by the U.S. According to the National Marketing Institute, over 17% of customers are extremely engaged by green marketing, which engages 80% of consumers nowadays. These people belong to the LOHAS (Lifestyles of Health and Sustainability) demographic group.

Green products are ones that are not harmful to the environment and are manufactured from environmentally friendly components. They could be products or services developed by a firm to lessen its environmental effect. Consumers are becoming more aware of the importance of sustainability, prompting businesses to seek imaginative and inventive solutions to lessen their environmental imprint. As more consumers choose green products, manufacturers must adapt their production processes to fulfill these needs and remain competitive in the market. In this post, we will define green products and provide examples of ecologically friendly solutions available on the market today. A green product is one that has been developed to have a low environmental impact. items manufactured from recycled materials, items meant to be reused or recycled, and products made from renewable resources are examples of this (Team, 2023). Green products have a variety of drawbacks that should be examined prior to purchasing. For starters, green items may be more expensive than conventional products. This is due to the increased costs connected with developing ecologically friendly products that green firms frequently incur. Furthermore, green products may not outperform their conventional counterparts. A green cleaning product, for example, may not be as effective as a standard cleaning product.

Finally, finding green products in stores might be challenging. This is due to the fact that many merchants do not stock a diverse range of green products (Team, 2023).

On the other hand, there's a lot of related study about this topic however there are limited studies that tackle the consumers environmental consciousness, and attitude on green product as healthy options. Since most of the people are now aware of the environmental crisis like pollution, global warming, loss of forest etc. Also people are now conscious on what they buy and consume, people are now willing to expend more money to buy some green products or products that has a positive effect to the environment and most of the companies are adapting to green marketing in producing green products in order to give the demands of the consumers and to lessen the bad effect to the environment, there is a lack of comprehensive studies on this topic. Therefore, it is crucial to conduct this study to assess the consumers environmental consciousness, and attitude on green products as healthy option, to raise awareness to the people, to know the significance of green product, and to expand the idea of green products as a healthy option This study aimed to determine the consumers environmental consciousness and attitude on green products as healthy options.

Research Questions:

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of environmental consciousness of the consumers in a coffee shop in Metro Manila as to the following considerations.
 - 1.1. Environmental Issues
 - 1.2. Eco-Social Benefits
2. What is the attitude of the consumers in green products offered by the coffee shops?
 - 2.1. Environmental Issues
 - 2.2. Eco-Social Benefits
 - 2.3. Green product information
3. Is there a relationship between the consumers environmental consciousness and attitude on green products as assessed by the respondents?

METHODOLOGY

The Research Design is the framework of the general research methods and techniques that the Researchers will use to conduct the study successfully. The chosen Research design will allow the Researchers to accomplish the proper research methods that are suitable for the subject matter. The study will be using Descriptive Quantitative Research as the Research Design because the data that will be gathered throughout the Research will be presented in both numerical and descriptive form. Quantitative research involves the application of computational, and measurable, and the use of scientific devices to determine results. On the other hand, a Descriptive type of research design studies the characteristics of the population or a phenomenon and describes the situations that are being focused on in the study. Through the use of the combination of

both Descriptive and Quantitative research designs, the Researchers will be able to determine the Consumers Environmental Consciousness and Attitude on Green Products as Healthy Option. The Descriptive research design will be able to help the researchers' collect respondents from consumers about their experiences, feedback, and expectations in purchasing green products. This data will then be presented statistically for a much better understanding of the gathered responses.

Researchers used survey questionnaires to easily acquire data from the respondents. The survey will include both online and physical data gathering through Google Forms (Online) and Hard copy/ Printed survey questionnaires.

The researchers applied purposive sample technique which is also known as judgment, selective or subjective sampling in which relies on the researcher's own judgment when deciding which individuals of the population to include in the study. The study consists of general respondents in the population. Purposive sampling techniques is a non-probability technique for gathering a sample in which researchers select participants who will aid the study in achieving its objectives using their expertise. The researchers must consider these subjects' unique characteristics when assessing their research question. Stated differently, the participants are chosen by the researchers "on purpose." (Jim Frost, 2022) The whole population will be people for the consumers with a total hundred (100) respondents from random coffee shops. With the aid of this method, you can concentrate on a specific subgroup, important participants in a procedure, common cases, or exceptional situations.

Purposive sampling was used in the study to restrict the number of respondents to those who satisfied the predetermined requirements. Non-probability sampling is helpful for researchers that need to reach their target participants quickly.

The asserted qualifications of the respondents are as follows:

For the respondents,

- Respondents must be of legal age.
- Respondents must be a Filipino.
- Respondents must be customers of the coffee shop.
- Respondents must be familiar with green products.

Before the instrument was used in the study, survey questionnaires were divided into three parts in the order of Part 1. Respondent's Personal Profile, Part 2. Is the assessment on the level of environmental consciousness in restaurants. Part III is the Assessment on the Attitude of the Consumers Green Products.

After the suggestions and comments from the experts were considered, the instrument in the study was pretested to the thirty (30) random consumers in selected coffee shops in Manila. The reliability was determined using Cronbach's Alpha analysis which was orchestrated by our statistician.

2. Ranking. This will be used to determine the order of decreasing or increasing magnitude of variations. The largest frequency is ranked 1,2, 3 and so on down to the last rank and number.

3. Weighted Mean. The statistical tool ascends whether there will be an answer in determining the Consumers Environmental Consciousness and Attitude on Green Products as Healthy Options.

Formula

$$X_w = \frac{\sum f(W)}{N}$$

Where:

- X = weighted mean
- F = frequency
- W = weight of response
- N = total number of respondents

4. Spearman Rho Correlation Formula. The researchers will need to ensure the relationship of two (2) variables which are the Environmental Consciousness and Attitude.

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum D^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

Figure 4 Spearman Rho Formula

5. Likert Scale. The Likert scale is a commonly used survey rating scale to measure respondents' opinions or attitudes. In this research, the Likert scale will be employed to measure the effectiveness of green marketing practices in selected farm-to-table restaurants. Each response on the Likert scale responses will be assigned a numerical value (e.g., 1 to 5), indicating the level of agreement or disagreement. The scales that will be use are shown below.

Likert Scale for the Assessment on the Consumers Environmental Consciousness and Attitude on Green Products s Healthy Options.

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Symbol
5	4.2 – 5.0	Strongly Agree	SA
4	3.3 – 4.19	Agree A	

3	2.6 – 3.39	Moderately Agree	MA
2	1.8 – 2.59	Disagree	D
1	1.0 – 1.79	Strongly Disagree	SD

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of:

Table 1 Respondents as to Age:

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18-25 years old	70	70.00
26-33 years old	15	15.00
34-40 years old	7	7.00
Above 40 years old	8	8.00
TOTAL	100	100.00

As revealed in Table 1, there are 70, or 70%, of the respondents whose age ranges from 18-25 years old. There are 15 respondents, or 15 % whose age ranges from 26 to 33 years old. There are 7 or 7% of the respondents whose age ranges from 34 to 40 years old, and the remaining are 40 years old and older, with 8 or 8% of the respondents.

Summarily, most of the respondents are 18-25 years old with 70 (70%), 26–33 years old with 15 (15%), 34–40 years old with 7 (7%), and the last is 40 years old and older with 8 (8%). In this result, it was shown that most of the respondents are in the age range of 18-25 years old as this is affected by the place where the researchers gathered the data. Most of the coffee shops where the researchers gathered the data are located in the University-belt in Metro Manila as this appeared in the results that most of the respondents are students.

Table 2 Respondents as to Sex:

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	53	53.00
Female	47	47.00
TOTAL	100	100.00

Table 2 reveals that 53, or 53%, of the respondents are male. There are 47, or 47%, of the respondents who are female; This gives the impression that most of the respondents are single, with 53 (53%) and 47 (47 %) are female.

Table 3 Respondents as to Frequency of Visits in Coffee Shop:

Frequency of Visits in Coffee Shop	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Always	10	10.00
Often (Several times a week)	50	50.00
Sometimes (Once a week)	22	22.00
Rarely (Once a month)	18	18.00
TOTAL	100	100.00

Table 3 reveals that consumers always visit restaurants, with 10 or 10% of the respondents. 50 or 50% of the respondents often or several times a week; 22 or 22% of the respondents sometimes visit restaurants; the remaining 18 or 18% of the respondents rarely or once a month visit restaurants. This gives the impression that most of the respondents visit a restaurant often, or several times a week.

The result of often or several times a week is connected to the result of Table No. 1.1 Respondents as to Age, since most of the respondents are students, their budget is limited to buying coffee only several times a week and not every day as they are still mostly depending on their allowances.

Sub Problem No. 1

Table 4 Assessment of the Level of Environmental Consciousness of the Respondents in a coffee shop in Metro Manila (Summarized Table)

Assessment of the Level of Environmental Consciousness of the Respondents in a coffee shop in Metro Manila	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Environmental Issues	4.50	Strongly Agree	1
Eco-Social Benefits	4.50	Strongly Agree	1
General Weighted Mean	4.50	Strongly Agree	

Table 4 presents the summarized result of the assessment table of the level of environmental consciousness of the respondents in a coffee shop in Metro Manila. It can be noticed that both variables which are “Environmental Issues” and “Eco-Social Benefits” are tied with a mean of 4.50 which made them both ranked first. The general weighted mean of the two variables is 4.50 and is interpreted as strongly agreed upon by the respondents that they are strongly aware of the issues in these variables.

Table 5 Assessment of the Level of Environmental Consciousness of the Respondents in a coffee shop in Metro Manila in terms of Environmental Issues:

Environmental Issues	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. I am concerned about environmental pollution.	4.55	Strongly Agree	1
2. I am aware of energy conservation.	4.47	Agree	3
3. I am concerned about the overconsumption of water.	4.49	Agree	2
General Weighted Mean	4.50	Strongly Agree	

Table 5 presents the assessment of the level of environmental consciousness of the respondents in a coffee shop in Metro Manila in terms of environmental issues. It can be noticed that the indicator that ranked first was the indicator that states, “I am concerned about environmental pollution.” with a mean of 4.55. This indicator was strongly agreed upon by the respondents.

It was followed by the indicator that states, “I am concerned about the overconsumption of water.” with a mean of 4.49. Lastly was the indicator that states, “I am aware of energy conservation.” with a mean of 4.47. All these indicators were agreed upon by the respondents.

In general, the respondents strongly agreed with the assessment of the level of environmental consciousness of the respondents in a coffee shop in Metro Manila in terms of environmental issues with a general weighted mean of 4.50.

Relative to the findings Nek Mahmud et.al (2020) research, Bangladeshi mentioned that Consumers are more willing to change their lifestyle and purchase environmentally friendly products if they are less expensive, even though the prices of green products are greater than those of conventional products. Thus, the best way to address environmental issues in a restaurant is to put sustainable practices in place, such as composting or donating excess food, minimizing carbon footprints by sourcing local and organic ingredients, using eco-friendly packaging and utensils made of recyclable or biodegradable materials, conserving water and energy through energyefficient appliances and practices, and educating customers and staff about the value of sustainability. To lessen the environmental effect of producing beef, think about introducing programs like providing plant-based menu options. Restaurants may significantly reduce the environmental impact and support a more sustainable food business by implementing these strategies. In addition, implementing sustainable practices, such as reducing food waste through donations or composting, using ecofriendly packaging and utensils, sourcing local and organic ingredients, conserving water and energy, and educating staff and patrons on sustainability, are important ways

for restaurants to address environmental issues. Adding plant-based menu alternatives can help lessen the impact that producing meat has on the environment. Taking these steps, restaurants may reduce their environmental impact and support a more sustainable food sector

Table 6 Assessment of the Level of Environmental Consciousness of the Respondents in a coffee shop in Metro Manila in terms of Eco-Social Benefits

Eco-Social Benefits	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. I am willing to take actions that are more environmentally friendly.	4.53	Strongly Agree	4
2. I prefer recyclable products.	4.61	Strongly Agree	1
3. I prefer products that have eco-friendly packaging.	4.55	Strongly Agree	2
4. I prefer products that are locally sourced (buying local ingredients)	4.51	Strongly Agree	5
5. It is important to me that the products I use do not harm the environment.	4.54	Strongly Agree	3
General Weighted Mean	4.50	Strongly Agree	

Table 6 presents the assessment of the level of environmental consciousness of the respondents in a coffee shop in Metro Manila in terms of eco-social benefits. It can be noticed that the indicator that ranked first was the indicator that states, “I prefer recyclable products.” with a mean of 4.61. It was followed by the indicator that states, “I prefer products that have eco-friendly packaging.” with a mean of 4.55. Next to it were “It is important to me that the products I use do not harm the environment.” and “I am willing to take actions that are more environmentally friendly.” with a mean of 4.54 and 4.53 respectively. Lastly was the indicator that states, “I prefer products that are locally sourced (buying local ingredients).” with a mean of 4.51. All these indicators were strongly agreed upon by the respondents. In general, the respondents strongly agreed with the assessment of the level of environmental consciousness of the respondents in a coffee shop in Metro Manila in terms of eco-social benefits with a general weighted mean of 4.55.

The findings, along with those of Boztepe (2012) and Suresh (2014), mentioned that green marketing is a phenomenon that raises public health awareness, lengthens life expectancy, and promotes environmental consciousness. The primary cause of the rise in awareness is the marketing campaigns run by businesses that use a green marketing approach. Public health is improved using specific green products, which thus raises the average life expectancy in society. This is also related to the findings of Khatabook (2012),

who mentioned that the environment may benefit from green marketing as well. Businesses may contribute to the reduction of resources required in the manufacturing, packing, and delivery of their goods by endorsing environmentally friendly items. In addition to preserving natural resources, this can also lower waste and pollution. Implementing sustainable practices, such as procuring products locally to support small-scale farmers and reduce carbon emissions from transportation, is a good way for restaurants to address eco-social advantages. To guarantee fair treatment of vendors and laborers along the supply chain, use fair trade practices. Prioritize cutting back on food waste by recycling leftovers, limiting portion sizes, and donating extra food to nearby nonprofits. Promote social concerns and environmental awareness in the community by holding events, workshops, or fundraisers. Restaurants must implement these strategies to improve the social fabric of their communities and lessen their negative environmental effects.

Sub Problem No. 2

Table 7 Attitude of the consumers in green products offered by the coffee shops in Metro Manila (Summarized Table)

Attitude of the consumers in green products offered by the coffee shops in Metro Manila	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Environmental Issues	4.40	Agree	2
Eco-Social Benefits	4.14	Agree	3
Green Products Information	4.44	Agree	1
General Weighted Mean	4.33	Agree	

Table 7 presents the summarized assessment table of the attitude of the respondents on green products offered by the coffee shops. It can be noticed that the variable that ranked first was the “Green Products Information” with a mean of 4.44. It was followed by the variable “Environmental Issues” with a mean of 4.40. Lastly was the variable “Eco-Social Benefits” with a mean of 4.14. All these variables were agreed upon by the respondents.

In general, the respondents agreed with the assessment of the attitude of the respondents on green products offered by the coffee shops with a general weighted mean of 4.33. This indicates that the respondents are strongly aware of green products and agree that they applied their awareness to their attitude.

Table 8 Attitude of the consumers in green products offered by the coffee shops in terms of Environmental Issues

Environmental Issues	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. I take environmental considerations into account while buying green products.	4.32	Agree	3
2. I support products that prioritize water conservation efforts.	4.39	Agree	2
3. I appreciate products that adhere to or exceed environmental regulations reflecting a commitment to compliance and responsibility	4.48	Agree	1
General Weighted Mean	4.40	Agree	

Table 8 presents the assessment of the attitude of the respondents on green products offered by the coffee shops in terms of environmental issues. It can be noticed that the indicator that ranked first was the indicator that states, “I appreciate products that adhere to or exceed environmental regulations reflecting a commitment to compliance and responsibility” with a mean of 4.48. It was followed by the indicator that states, “I support products that prioritize water conservation efforts.” with a mean of 4.39. Lastly was the indicator that states, “I take environmental considerations into account while buying green products.” with a mean of 4.32. All these indicators were agreed upon by the respondents.

In general, the respondents strongly agreed with the assessment of the attitude of the respondents on green products offered by the coffee shops in terms of environmental issues with a general weighted mean of 4.40.

Relative to the findings of Wang et.al (2016), mentioned in their study, the growing environmental consciousness in the restaurant sector has led to a trend towards green dining. Studies show that environmentally conscious consumers are willing to pay more for green products, and green marketing directly and indirectly influences purchase intention through brand image. Research findings repeatedly indicate that consumers who care about the environment are prepared to pay a higher price for goods and services that share their values and support environmental sustainability. This readiness to pay extra shows a dedication to backing companies that value environmentally sustainable operations, even at the expense of increased expenses. Furthermore, through influencing consumer perception and brand image, green marketing is essential in influencing purchase intentions. Businesses can attract environmentally conscious customers and

improve their brand reputation by successfully communicating their commitment to sustainability through their marketing methods. Therefore, making investments in green projects and integrating them into marketing campaigns can increase sales and cultivate favorable connections with environmentally conscientious customers. Companies can directly impact consumers' purchasing intentions by appealing to their values and indirectly improve brand loyalty and reputation when they successfully express their commitment to sustainability through their marketing activities. For these reasons, integrating green marketing campaigns into company plans can help draw in eco-aware clients and boost revenue.

Table 9 Attitude of the consumers in green products offered by the coffee shops in terms of Eco-Social Benefits

Eco-Social Benefits	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. While buying, I read the product label to see if the contents are eco-friendly.	4.09	Agree	2
2. For healthy living, I will buy green products, even if it is expensive.	4.01	Agree	3
3. I am interested in new and innovative green products that are environmentally beneficial.	4.33	Agree	1
General Weighted Mean	4.14	Agree	

Table 9 presents the assessment of the attitude of the respondents on green products offered by the coffee shops in terms of eco-social benefits. It can be noticed that the indicator that ranked first was the indicator that states, "I am interested in new and innovative green products that are environmentally beneficial." with a mean of 4.33. It was followed by the indicator that states, "While buying, I read the product label to see if the contents are eco-friendly." with a mean of 4.09. Lastly was the indicator that states, "For healthy living, I will buy green products, even if it is expensive." with a mean of 4.01. All these indicators were agreed upon by the respondents.

In general, the respondents strongly agreed with the assessment of the attitude of the respondents on green products offered by the coffee shops in terms of eco-social benefits with a general weighted mean of 4.14.

Relative to the findings of Wang et.al. (2016), mentioned in their study, the growing environmental consciousness in the restaurant sector has led to a trend towards green dining. Studies show that environmentally conscious consumers are willing to pay more for green products, and green marketing directly and indirectly influences purchase

intention through brand image. With an emphasis on the eco-social advantages, customers' perceptions of the green items that coffee shops sell are becoming more and more favorable. Many customers actively seek out coffee shops that adhere to these values because they value sustainability and social responsibility. Customers are prepared to pay more for goods that encourage ethical work practices, help local communities, and improve the environment. Consumer views and purchasing decisions are significantly influenced by factors including convenience, brand recognition, and the efficient communication of eco-social efforts. Coffee shops that put an emphasis on environmental stewardship, ethical sourcing, and transparency can benefit from the growing demand for eco-friendly products and cultivate a loyal customer base among socially and ecologically conscientious consumers. Due to their advantages for the environment and society, customers are becoming more and more disposed to prefer green items that coffee shops sell. Customers are making ethical and sustainable practices a top priority when making purchases as a result of their increased understanding of social and environmental concerns. From their perspective, buying green items is an excellent method to support ethical labor practices, improve the environment, and enhance community well-being. Coffee shops are likely to draw in and keep consumers who value ethical consumption if they highlight these eco-social benefits through community involvement, eco-friendly packaging, and transparent sourcing.

Table 10 Attitude of the consumers in green products offered by the coffee shops in terms of Green Product Information

Green Product Information	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
4. I value a brand that provides accurate and transparent information about green products	4.49	Agree	1
5. I understand the information on ecofriendly packaging (reusable plastic containers, paper cups, wooden spoons, and forks).	4.44	Agree	2
6. I have a more favorable opinion of products that feature an eco-label.	4.38	Agree	3
General Weighted Mean	4.44	Agree	

Table 10 presents the assessment of the attitude of the respondents on green products offered by the coffee shops in terms of green product information. It can be noticed that the indicator that ranked first was the indicator that states, "I value a brand that provides accurate and transparent information about green products." with a mean

of 4.49. It was followed by the indicator that states, “I understand the information on ecofriendly packaging (reusable plastic containers, paper cups, wooden spoons, and forks).” with a mean of 4.44. Lastly was the indicator that states, “I have a more favorable opinion of products that feature an eco-label.” with a mean of 4.38. All these indicators were agreed upon by the respondents.

In general, the respondents strongly agreed with the assessment of the attitude of the respondents on green products offered by the coffee shops in terms of green product information with a general weighted mean of 4.44.

Relative to the findings of Rajendran et al. (2019), customers are more concerned about the caliber of green packaging. However, in Bangladesh, most consumers are aware of environmentally friendly products but are not worried about green marketing. Information about green products aids consumers in understanding how the products they purchase will affect the environment. Their level of knowledge empowers individuals to make well-informed decisions by considering variables such as waste generation, emissions, and resource utilization. Information on green products is essential because it enables customers to make decisions that are in line with environmental principles. Transparency on a product's environmental friendliness enables businesses to pursue environmentally friendly practices and supports sustainability. In addition to increasing consumer confidence, this information encourages competition among companies to create greener products, which eventually leads to beneficial environmental change. It also lessens the dangers of greenwashing, ensures regulatory compliance, and encourages resource efficiency across supply chains. In general, green product information promotes sustainable production and consumption, which is advantageous for society and the environment.

Consumers are empowered to support eco-friendly activities when products are transparent about their sustainability qualities, including emissions, resource utilization, and environmental impact. This information pushes businesses to prioritize sustainability in their operations while also encouraging environmental stewardship. In addition, it promotes consumer and company trust, encourages innovation toward more environmentally friendly options, and guarantees regulatory compliance. To put it simply, green product information is essential to achieve sustainability objectives and promote a healthy planet for present and future generations.

Sub Problem No. 3

Table 11 On the Significant Relationship Between the Level of Environmental Consciousness of the Respondents in a coffee shop in Metro Manila and Attitude of the Respondents on Green Products Offered by the Coffee Shops.

	N	SD	Mean	Pearson r	Interpretation	Decision
Environmental Consciousness	100	0.57	4.53	0.72	Strong Positive	Reject Null Hypothesis
Attitude on Green Products as Healthy Options		0.6	4.33			

Table 11 presents the test of the significant relationship between the level of environmental consciousness of the respondents in a coffee shop in Metro Manila and the attitude of the respondents on green products offered by the coffee shops. The table shows that the Pearson r value is 0.72 which means a high positive correlation between the two variables. Null hypothesis should be rejected which implies a significant relationship.

Conclusions

Based on the foregoing findings, the following are the conclusions of the study.

1. The respondents strongly agree with all indicators assessing their environmental consciousness regarding environmental issues, with a grand mean of 4.50. The respondents exhibit a high level of environmental consciousness, as evidenced by their strong agreement with all indicators assessing environmental issues. The grand mean score of 4.50 further supports this, indicating a consistent and robust alignment with environmentally conscious attitudes and behaviors across the board. This suggests a significant commitment among respondents to consider and address environmental concerns in their decision-making processes and daily lives. In terms of eco-social benefits, the respondents strongly agree with all indicators assessing their environmental consciousness, with a grand mean of 4.50. The respondents demonstrate strong agreement with all indicators assessing their environmental consciousness regarding eco-social benefits. With a grand mean score of 4.50, it is evident that they are highly attuned to the interconnectedness of environmental and social issues. This suggests a deep commitment to considering the broader implications of their actions for both the environment and society. Their consistent alignment with eco-socially conscious attitudes and behaviors underscores a collective dedication to promoting sustainability and social responsibility in their daily lives and decision-making processes.

2. This indicates that overall, respondents exhibit a favorable view or agreement regarding environmental concerns. The weighted mean values of 4.48, 4.39, and 4.32 for the indicators connected to environmental issues resulted in a grand mean of 4.40, which is orally translated as "Agree." Their combined answers show a strong recognition of and alignment with environmental issues and ideals as determined by the indicators. With respect to the indicators of eco-social benefits, the weighted mean values of 4.33, 4.09, and 4.01 came together to provide a grand mean of 4.14, which may be orally interpreted as "Agree." This indicates that respondents generally seem to be in agreement or have a good attitude toward the advantages that have been evaluated. As a group, they show that they are committed to sustainability and social responsibility and that they recognize and agree that environmental and social concerns are intertwined. Regarding the green product information, this indicates that overall, respondents express a positive stance or agreement assessed. The weighted mean values of 4.49, 4.44, and 4.38 for the indicators related to green product information culminated in a grand mean of 4.44, which is verbally interpreted as "Agree." Their replies collectively demonstrate a need for accountability and openness in sustainability programs, as well as a positive recognition and alignment with the significance of truthful and educational communication about environmentally friendly products.
3. According to the data presented, there seems to be a substantial correlation between the respondents' attitudes toward the green items that coffee shops in Metro Manila sell and their degree of environmental consciousness.
4. There is a significant positive correlation between the two variables, as indicated by the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) of 0.72. There appears to be a strong positive association between the degree of environmental consciousness and coffee shops' favorable attitude toward green items. It would be fair to reject the null hypothesis considering the high correlation coefficient and the suggestion of a substantial association. This implies that there is proof in favor of the theory that the degree of environmental consciousness affects people's perceptions of green items.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions, the following are the recommendations of the study.

1. In terms of promotion, coffee shops/restaurants should focus on promoting green practices to the consumers by educating customers, informing clients about your environmental programs, and inviting them to get involved by offering advice on how to lessen their own environmental effect about environmental issues and social concerns in the way of:

1.1 Putting green labels on their packaging: Putting posters in their physical shops about environmental sustainability, posters and placards with educational content should be hung throughout the store to raise awareness of environmental problems associated with coffee production, such as waste production, water use, and deforestation.

1.2 Organize community activities such as "Green Coffee Talks" or workshops covering subjects like composting, eco-friendly living, and the environmental effects of coffee farming to raise awareness among consumers.

1.3 Partnerships with Environmental Organizations: Join forces for events, fund-raisers, or awareness campaigns with nearby environmental organizations. This partnership has the potential to spread the word and reach more people.

1.4 Social Media Campaigns: Post advice, information, and updates about environmental issues via social media. Invite clients to participate in the discussion and to share their own environmentally friendly habits.

2. In terms of operational practices, coffee shops/restaurants should prioritize sustainable practices to influence the attitude of the consumers rather than doing it for marketing purposes. This practice connects to the use of:

2.1 Green packing: For takeaway orders and retail products, use environmentally friendly packing materials made of recycled or biodegradable materials.

2.2 Reusable Utensils and Cups: Provide discounts or other incentives to patrons who bring their own reusable cups. For individuals who would rather use throwaway solutions, use compostable or biodegradable cups and cutlery.

2.3 Choosing Sustainable Coffee Beans: Look for coffee beans certified organic, Fair Trade, or Rainforest Alliance, which promote socially and environmentally conscious methods. Or for restaurants, using plant-based ingredients instead of pure meat to reduce the environmental effect.

2.4 Local and Organic Ingredients: To lessen the carbon footprint caused by transportation and to help out local farmers, try to source ingredients that are produced locally and organically.

2.5 Water Conservation: To cut down on the demand for bottled water, install water-saving fixtures on faucets and think about utilizing a water filter system.

2.6 Minimize food waste by providing smaller portion sizes, precisely estimating demand, and donating extra food to nearby nonprofit organizations.

3. In terms of purchase intentions, consumers should prioritize buying from coffee shops/restaurants that do:

3.1 Sustainable practices on daily operations

3.2 Eco-friendly products/merchandise from the coffee shops/restaurants

3.3 Supporting the usage of green products such as paper cups, paper straws, wooden spork, and recyclable packaging.

3.4 Support the coffee shops/restaurants that do local sourcing or local productions to promote the local farmers and producers, in this way, it can reduce the carbon footprints which is better for the environment.

4. In terms of consumer environmental practices, consumers should practice the change of use from disposable usage to reusable and quality utensils. The consumers should substitute the use of:

4.1 Disposable Styrofoam cups to bring personal tumbler cups.

4.2 Disposable plastic spoons and forks to metal spoons and forks

4.3 Disposable plastic straws to bringing metal straws.

4.4 Disposable unrecyclable tissue to personal handkerchiefs to reduce the usage of tissue.

5. Future researchers should utilize this study and improve the study about green products and environmental concerns that connect to the hospitality industry, the researcher's recommendation to improve this study is to research innovative and unique ways to influence people when it comes to healthy lifestyles that are also healthy to the environment and to research how to effectively raise awareness to the people that has no intention to change lifestyle to help sustain the environment.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study was held accountable and responsible for the confidentiality of our respondents and other people involved in this research. The researcher's adviser went over and gave the research instrument used in the research. Researcher survey instruments will be made available depending on how the problem is stated. The individuals who took part were able to back up demonstrating their cooperation by signing the consent form and acknowledging that they have done so that they accepted to participate after fully comprehending the survey's requirements. During the process of completing the questionnaires that were provided to them. Along with the consent form survey's goals and purpose, which are beneficial to both the study and a commitment to keeping participants' personal information confidential. As well, Both the respondents' data and the data of the respondents will be treated privately and confidentially in the implementation of safety regulations.

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